

Efficient Point to Multipoint Transfers Across Datacenters

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Global Placement of Datacenters and Inter-Datacenter Networks

- Benefits**
- ✓ Better communication across datacenters
 - ✓ Increased reliability
 - ✓ Load balancing
 - ✓ Easier to get data closer to users
 - Lower RTT to users (Higher Avg Throughput)
 - Less hops to users (Bandwidth Savings)

Point to Multipoint (P2MP) Transfers: An Abstraction Model

Current Solutions and Their Shortcomings

- | Solution | Shortcomings |
|--------------------------------------|--|
| Separate Unicast Transfers | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Wastes Bandwidth ❖ May increase Completion Times |
| Multicasting (Network-Driven) | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Trees Far From Optimal <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➢ No attention to resource utilization ➢ Trees built gradually with joins/leaves ❖ Complex Session Management ❖ Example: IP Multicast |
| Multicasting (Client-Driven) | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Limited visibility into network status ❖ Limited control over routing ❖ Example: Overlay Networks |
| Store-and-Forward (SnF) | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Storage and bandwidth costs on intermediate datacenters ❖ Can lead to excessive delays ❖ Complexity (running SnF agents, chunking and reassembly, etc.) |

Our Solution: DCCast

- ✓ For every P2MP transfer, send traffic to all receivers over a single *Forwarding Tree*
 - Reduced bandwidth usage
- ✓ Forwarding Tree Selection (at controller)
 - Chosen by a controller with global view of network status
 - Simple weight assignment to edges
 - Minimum weight Steiner tree selection
 - Load balancing / Reducing completion times
- ✓ Rate-Allocation (controller) and Rate-Limiting (senders)
 - Slotted timeline with fixed rates during timeslots

Tree Selection and Rate-Allocation: Upon Request Arrival

- | Tree Selection | Rate-Allocation |
|--|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Input: L_e (outstanding load on every edge e) and V_R (request volume) ✓ Every edge e gets a weight of $W_e = V_R + L_e$ ✓ Minimum weight Steiner tree \rightarrow Forwarding Tree of R ✓ Many heuristics available for Steiner tree selection | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ According to FCFS: Simple, no rate-recalculations ✓ Guaranteed completion times assuming no failures ✓ Investigation of more policies (e.g. Fair Sharing) in future <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➢ Any scheduling policy can be used on top of DCCast's forwarding tree selection |

Evaluations

Future Work

- ❖ Improving Mean TCT
 - Multiple trees each connected to a subset of receivers (addressing slow receivers)
 - Parallel trees to same subsets of receivers (increasing throughput)
 - Applying SRPT with only BW preemption (trees selected upon request arrivals)
 - Combining forwarding trees with store-and-forward
- Applying batching techniques for bursty arrival patterns (e.g. apply SJF policy to batches)
- Applying the Fair Sharing policy (rather than FCFS)
- ❖ Handling Failures
 - Proactive approaches (leaving spare capacity, backup trees)
 - Reactive approaches (rescheduling affected transfers, local activation)